

Description

The European project WASTE4Think seeks to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto, demonstrating the value of integrating and validating a set of 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain.

The Project started in June 2016 and has a duration of 42 months. The consortium consists of a total of 19 partners including 5 public agencies and administration, 1 research organization, 2 universities, 7 SMEs, 2 large enterprises, 1 cluster and 1 NGO. The total budget is 10.5M€ with a contribution of 8.8M€ from EC.

Objectives

- To reduce generation of waste thanks to prevention and cooperative activities
- To improve the integral waste management services reducing their management costs and the GHG emissions.
- To identify the waste products with a low recyclability potential and to propose eco-innovative solutions.
- To promote behavioural changes by awareness campaigns and new educational tools to foster more sustainable consumption and production habits
- To reduce the amount of primary waste deposited in landfill
- To assess the transferability to the market of the new proposed eco-innovative solutions.

Expected results

- 8% reduction of waste generation
- 20% increase in waste sorting
- 10% saving of management costs
- 10% reduction of GHG emissions

ZAMUDIO

HALANDRI

SEVESO

CASCAIS

Eco-Solutions

Pilots

The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology, and will be demonstrated in 4 complementary urban areas in Europe.

- C** The coastal municipality of CASCAIS (PT)
- Z** The industrialized area of ZAMUDIO (ES)
- S** The residential town of SEVESO (IT)
- H** The business city of HALANDRI (GR)

COORDINATOR

DeustoTech

zabala innovation consulting

Zamudio Udala

aclima Basque Environment Cluster

Green Technologies Ltd Technical Studies & Constructions

EnBio LTD

ΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΟΝ ΠΑΤΡΩΝ UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS

Δήμος Χαλανδρίου

SERIOUS GAMES INTERACTIVE

ARS AMBIENTE ANALISI, RICERCHI E SERVIZI PER L'AMBIENTE

LEGAMBIENTE

SOFTline SOFTWARE E SERVIZI PER L'AMBIENTE

MOBA MOBILE AUTOMATION

CASCAIS AMBIENTE Gestão do Ambiente Terrestre e Marítimo

ECOLOGIA Agència d'Ecologia Urbana de Barcelona

VIRTUALWARE

ENGINEERING

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995.

The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contains.

MOVING TOWARDS
LIFE CYCLE THINKING
BY INTEGRATING
ADVANCED WASTE
MANAGEMENT
SYSTEMS

WASTE4think.eu

f t in YouTube